

MANAGEMENT OF STRESS AND MOTIVATION OF EMPLOYEES

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Abstract:

Stress is a physical and emotional reaction when everyone encounters the various challenges of life. It will lead to mental unrest. Stress is the body's automatic response to any physical or mental demand placed on it. Stress is a negative concept and creates a negative mental attitude in the mind of individuals. The various reasons for stress in organizations are over work load, role ambiguity, role conflict, isolation, lack of family-social support etc. Moderate stress relating to job aspects is essential because it helps to improve the performance of employees. But over stress leads to mental dissatisfaction, conflict, absenteeism, turnover etc. so every organizations must care their employees from having over stress. Division of work, prioritizing & organizing, yoga & meditation, balanced time schedule, improving emotional intelligence etc are some of the ways to minimize stress. The concept of motivation can be effectively used to remove stress from our organization. Different motivational techniques such as financial incentives, appreciation, personal encouragement, training and development programs, seminar & workshops etc. will help to throw away stress from organizations, if complete stress had been removed, and motivation is given, a complete & strategic organizational change will take place in organization..

Keywords:

Stress Management, motivational techniques, mental unrest, motivational techniques, personal encouragement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In olden days, human resources were considered only as a factor of production i.e. an instrument for the organization to accomplish organizational objectives. But changes take place in each and every corner of the business world, organizations are compelled to consider human resources as an asset for the survival of organizations. Rather than concentrating on the factors of production, the organizations are required to concentrate on human resources for their effective functioning. Now, a separate department had set up to manage human resources namely Human Resource Department. The main functions of this department are to provide training, motivation, and effective management of human resources of an organization to make them efficient.

At present, the organizations are required to care on the personal, organizational problems of every employee. Rather than providing better salary and working environment, the organizations must ensure the satisfaction of employees. If employees are dissatisfied in any aspect of organization, they will be stressed, it will leads to absenteeism, inactive in work place and finally the turnover of efficient employees. This indicates that extra care must be given to human resources while handling with them.

Motivation is an important technique which can be used for reducing the job stress of an individual. If proper motivation techniques are provided ,(motivation does not mean training and development class but also it includes so many other techniques) employees will be satisfied , if they are satisfied ,they will be active in their work places ,which increases organizational productivity that may lead to a complete positive change of an organization otherwise all these adversely affect the organization . So management of stress and motivation of employees are essential for the change of an organization.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

- To find out the role of motivation, and stress management in organizational change

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- To find out the various reasons for stress ,its effects and ways to manage them
- To find out the need for motivation in organizations ,various motivation techniques and its effect in organizations
- To find out how the stress management and motivation can be effectively used for organizational change

For the present study secondary data from various books, journals, magazines, reports and websites are used.*

3. STRESS MANAGEMENT

3.1.STRESS

Stress is a physical and emotional reaction when everyone encounters the various challenges of life. It will lead to mental unrest. Stress is the body's automatic response to any physical or mental demand placed on it. Moderate levels of stress may actually improve performance and efficiency, but too much stress may cause an unproductive anxiety level. So stress to an extent is good but beyond the extent that will affect individuals badly. The various factors affecting stress are School, Work, Family, Relationships, Financial problems, Health/illness, Living environment etc.

3.1.1. REASONS FOR STRESS IN ORGANISATIONS

The following are the reasons for stress in organizations;

- **Over work load:** over work load may create job stress in organizations. There are two types of over workloads *.Qualitative work load* and *Quantitative work load*. Qualitative work load refers a work given to an employee is beyond his capacity; he is unable to perform that work by using his physical or mental capacities. But quantitative work load means excess of work than he can actually perform.
- **Higher target:** Modern business organizations are target based. Every employee will have a target to attain. If the organization assigned a target that he/she cannot attain creates job stress.
- **Role ambiguity:** sometimes there may be ambiguity in the work to be done by employees. They are not clear about their role and nature of work to be performed, may create stress in their job place.
- **Role conflict:** it is also a part of role ambiguity. If role of employees are not specified, may create role ambiguity may leads to conflict.
- **Isolation:** isolation is another reason for job stress. When an employee felt that he is isolated or he is not cared by others will lead to stress
- **Pressure from superior staff:** in many organizations, the superiors will give orders and the subordinates are compelled to perform it. Pressure to an extent is good for their performance but over pressure may leads to job stress.
- **Lack of job security :** job security reduces stress but job insecurity increase the stress
- **Threat to professional and personal status:** if an employee is asked to perform such tasks which is a threat to his professional or personal status leads to stress.
- **Occupational demands :** if the employees are not provided with adequate facilities for their work ,the organization does not recognizing their demands required for working is an indicator of job stress
- **Inter personal conflict:** inter personal conflict may arise between same level of employees, superior-subordinates etc.
- **organizational changes**
- **lack of social support**
- **personal problems**
- **indecent feelings**
- **feeling of ignoring.....etc.,** may create job stress in organizations

Table 1: EFFECTS OF STRESS

Physical	Emotional	Intellectual	Organizational
1.Sleep disturbances 2.Head ache 3.Mind upset 4.High B.P	1.Deprssion 2.Anxiety	1.lack of concentration 2.loss of memory 3.in effective in motivation	1.Absenteesm 2.Labour turnover 3.Poor time keeping 4.Poor performance 5.Low morale 6.Employee complaints 7.Poor productivity

3.1.2. METHODS FOR STRESS MANAGEMENT

- Express your feelings with co-workers, subordinates and with superiors with an open mind instead of boosting it.
- Be willing to compromise with others, listen to others words, recognize it.
- Be more sensitive in all organizational concerns
- Manage time better will leads to timely completion of work .if the entire work has been timely finished ,there will be no stress
- Re frame existing problems ,identify different solutions for solving problem ,and reduce the problem to the possible extent
- Look at the big picture of problem and stress ,we realize that our problem is smaller as compared with the big picture ,leads to some relaxation in our mind ,is a method to manage stress
- Adjust standards of work .be ready to accept changes, do not deal any matter with fixed mind, and fluctuate accordingly.
- Focus positively with every matters of organizational problems, do not focus any problem with a negative mind. Positive minded peoples never face stress.
- Do not try to control uncontrollable, if any one tries to control uncontrollable variables, leads to high stress. If we realized that the particular subject matter cannot be controlled with our own capacity, just avoid it.
- Share feelings with friends, collegiate, co-workers etc. even if it is positive or negative .sharing of positive feelings help to boost them and sharing of negative feelings helps to minimize them
- Learn to forgive. Do not be possessive in organizational concerns. If any mistake have been occurred during the work from our subordinates or co-workers ,do not deal with angry ,advise them ,forgive and motivate them
- Set time for relaxing ,relaxation is a best method of stress management ,when relaxing ,our mind will be cool always ,cooled minded persons will not face stress and its consequences

- Regular exercising will also help to reduce stress. Exercise is also a method of relaxation
- Meditation is a method of yoga, breathing etc. will more effectively used as a method to manage stress.
- If any one feels that ,exercise ,meditation ,relaxation etc. are not effective in their life to manage stress ,it is advisable to attend for a counseling with psychiatrist or with counselors ,their treatments will help you to reduce stress
- Set boundaries of your work, think and act within the boundaries. This boundary must be fixed by ourselves and don't with the compulsion of others
- Plan major life style changes, if some life style changes had taken place ,stress can be managed effectively .wake up in the early morning ,walking spend more time with spouse and children ,etc. may leads to minimize stress
- Re size limitations, create a positive mind always that 'I can do 'nothing is impossible 'etc. No one is perfect in all concerns. Weakness is not a problem and tries to overcome it.
- Prioritize concepts and duties to be performed. Do most important duties first, then second and so on. if highly prioritized and important works are completed ,there will be no important works to be performed ,so stress to a large extent can be removed
- Improve communication with others, be open minded, cool, be joke with others, communicate personal, organizational matters etc.
- Develop a positive attitude with every aspect. Avoid negative minded peoples. Look every aspect positively.
- Yoga and meditation also helps to reduce stress. Scientists proved that Yoga in the early morning will completely eliminate stress and will leads to fresh tension free mind
- Simplify the work ,divide the work to others too ,look everything in a simple way and approach with cool mind
- Collaborate and corporate with others
- Think globally
- Avoid negative minded peoples

3.2.3. TIPS TO REDUCE JOB STRESS

REDUCE JOB STRESS BY TAKING CARE OF YOURSELF

When stress at work interferes with your ability to perform in your job, manage your personal life, or adversely impacts your health, it's time to take action. Start by paying attention to your physical and emotional health. When your own needs are taken care of, you're stronger and more resilient to stress. The better you feel, the better equipped you'll be to manage work stress without becoming overwhelmed.

REDUCE JOB STRESS BY PRIORITIZING AND ORGANIZING

When job and workplace stress threatens to overwhelm you, there are simple steps you can take to regain control over yourself and the situation. Your newfound ability to maintain a sense of self-control in stressful situations will often be well-received by coworkers, managers, and subordinates alike, which can lead to better relationships at work. Here are some suggestions for reducing job stress by prioritizing and organizing your responsibilities.

TIME MANAGEMENT TIPS FOR REDUCING JOB STRESS

- **Create a balanced schedule.** Analyze your schedule, responsibilities, and daily tasks. All work and no play is a recipe for burnout. Try to find a balance between work and family life, social activities and solitary pursuits, daily responsibilities and downtime.
- **Don't over-commit yourself.** Avoid scheduling things back-to-back or trying to fit too much into one day. All too often, we underestimate how long things will take. If you've got too much on your plate, distinguish between the "shoulds" and the "musts." Drop tasks that aren't truly necessary to the bottom of the list or eliminate them entirely.
- **Try to leave earlier in the morning.** Even 10-15 minutes can make the difference between frantically rushing to your desk and having time to ease into your day. Don't add to your stress levels by running late.
- **Plan regular breaks.** Make sure to take short breaks throughout the day to take a walk or sit back and clear your mind. Also try to get away from your desk or work station for lunch. Stepping away from work to briefly relax and recharge will help you be more, not less, productive.

TASK MANAGEMENT TIPS FOR REDUCING JOB STRESS

- **Prioritize tasks.** Make a list of tasks you have to do, and tackle them in order of importance. Do the high-priority items first. If you have something particularly unpleasant to do, get it over with early. The rest of your day will be more pleasant as a result.
- **Break projects into small steps.** If a large project seems overwhelming, make a step-by-step plan. Focus on one manageable step at a time, rather than taking on everything at once.
- **Delegate responsibility.** You don't have to do it all yourself. If other people can take care of the task, why not let them? Let go of the desire to control or oversee every little step. You'll be letting go of unnecessary stress in the process.
- **Be willing to compromise.** When you ask someone to contribute differently to a task, revise a deadline, or change their behavior at work, be willing to do the same. Sometimes, if you can both bend a little, you'll be able to find a happy middle ground that reduces the stress levels for everyone concerned.

REDUCE JOB STRESS BY IMPROVING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Even if you're in a job where the environment has grown increasingly stressful, you can retain a large measure of self-control and self-confidence by understanding and practicing emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the ability to manage and use your emotions in positive and constructive ways. When it comes to satisfaction and success at work, emotional intelligence matters just as much as intellectual ability. Emotional intelligence is about communicating with others in ways that draw people to you, overcome differences, repair wounded feelings, and defuse tension and stress.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE WORKPLACE

Emotional intelligence in the workplace has four major components:

- **Self-awareness** – The ability to recognize your emotions and their impact while using gut feelings to guide your decisions.
- **Self-management** – The ability to control your emotions and behavior and adapt to changing circumstances.
- **Social awareness** – The ability to sense, understand, and react to other's emotions and feel comfortable socially.
- **Relationship management** – The ability to inspire, influence, and connect to others and manage conflict.

ELIMINATE SELF-DEFEATING BEHAVIORS

Many of us make job stress worse with negative thoughts and behavior. If you can turn around these self-defeating habits, you'll find employer-imposed stress easier to handle.

- **Resist perfectionism.** No project, situation, or decision is ever perfect, so trying to attain perfection on everything will simply add unnecessary stress to your day. When you set unrealistic goals for yourself or try to do too much, you're setting yourself up to fall short. Aim to do your best, no one can ask for more than that.
- **Clean up your act.** If you're always running late, set your clocks and watches fast and give yourself extra time. If your desk is a mess, file and throw away the clutter; just knowing where everything is saves time and cuts stress. Make to-do lists and cross off items as you accomplish them. Plan your day and stick to the schedule—you'll feel less overwhelmed.
- **Flip your negative thinking.** If you see the downside of every situation and interaction, you'll find yourself drained of energy and motivation. Try to think positively about your work, avoid negative-thinking co-workers, and pat yourself on the back about small accomplishments, even if no one else does.
- **Don't try to control the uncontrollable.** Many things at work are beyond our control—particularly the behavior of other people. Rather than stressing out over them, focus on the things you can control such as the way you choose to react to problems.

FOUR WAYS TO DISPEL STRESS

- **Take time away.** When stress is mounting at work, try to take a quick break and move away from the stressful situation. Take a stroll outside the workplace if possible, or spend a few minutes meditating in the break room. Physical movement or finding a quiet place to regain your balance can quickly reduce stress.
- **Talk it over with someone.** In some situations, simply sharing your thoughts and feelings with someone you trust can help reduce stress. Talking over a problem with someone who is both supportive and empathetic can be a great way to let off steam and relieve stress.
- **Connect with others at work.** Developing friendships with some of your co-workers can help buffer you from the negative effects of stress. Remember to listen to them and offer support when they are in need as well.
- **Look for humor in the situation.** When used appropriately, humor is a great way to relieve stress in the workplace. When you or those around you start taking things too seriously, find a way to lighten the mood by sharing a joke or funny story.

4. HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION

Dubin defines motivation as the complex of forces starting and keeping a person at work in an organization. Motivation is something that moves the person to action and continues him in the course of action already initiated. Motivation has close relationship with behavior of human beings. It is the function of every manager to identify every individual's weak points and help to overcome these weak points is the aim of motivation. The human resource manager must perform the duty of actuating people to work for accomplishment of objectives.

4.1. REASONS /NEEDS FOR H.R MANAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION

Human resource management is a vital part of every business organization. The human resources of every organizations must be managed well, must be motivated well for improving their efficiency which will leads to their active working which results in the improvement of organization's productivity. If an employee is motivated well, he will feel that he had been watched and cared by others, he will perform according to his maximum capacity. So proper motivation at each time must be provided to all the employees to have a positive mind in them which will be a useful tool in the hands of management for improving organizational efficiency.

The following are the reasons for H.R motivation:

- Quality, productivity, profitability, company image etc. are depend on training and co-ordination of employees.
- H.R.M is required to create proper understanding among the workers and management.
- All the employees must develop according to the requirements of organization and contribute for organizational goals.

- The operational efficiency of employees must be improved to face the challenges taken place in the business world such as technology, marketing etc.
- Labor laws affecting the demand for and supply of human resources.

Due to these reasons proper management of human resources are essential to every organization.

4.2.METHODS FOR H.R MOTIVATION

- **Employee participation in decision making** : The management of any organizations must consider their employees in the decision making process. If the employees are in the decision making process, they feel that they are the part of organization that is why the management is asking opinions etc. This feeling positively motivate the employees.
- **Maintain good employee employer relationship:** a good and effective employee employer relationship ensures the motivation of employees. Consider the employees as a friend and also employer as a friend .it will create a commitment among them
- **Appreciation:** appreciation and recognition of employees can be effectively used as a motivation technique of employees. Appreciate those employees who are extremely working hard for the organization, but never discourage employees who are unable to perform well.
- **Role model:** the managers and senior staff of the organization must be a role model to the junior staff. Because they are watching and growing like their superiors. so every person must be a role model to others in the work place and in their personal life too
- **Motivate by freedom and responsibility:** when the managers are using motivational techniques, it must be done by allocating responsibilities to them and provide sufficient freedom in their work place.
- **Let employees figure out, how they work best, don't give orders:** The employees of an organization must be allowed time to show what they can perform, if so they will work according to their best skill and efficiency.
- **Invest your employees with a sense of ownership in the business and they will be naturally motivated to perform**
- **Division of authority :**allocate certain authorities to the employees will encourage and motivate them in the work place
- **Coach and encourage :**The subordinates ,superiors and coworkers must coach ,train ,and encourage other regularly, will motivate the employees which will turn in to organizational efficiency
- **Focus on strength** : One of the main drawback of every person is that they will mainly focus on others weakness ,bad habits and worse speak about them .This concept must be thrown away from organizations ,focus on every one's strength ,feel them that they are good ,it will give a motivation to them
- **Do not over act with policies, regulations etc.:** If organizations over acted with new policies and strict regulations, it will adversely affect them. If rules are becoming stronger and stronger, employees have a general tendency to become loosen.

- **Provide better working environment** : Better working environment provides pleasant mind on every time to the employees ,reduces stress and motivate employees
- **Status means more than money**: status is more than money to every individuals. Re name the positions ,name tag etc. ensures their status and they will be automatically motivated
- **Personal thanks**: A simple ‘thank you ‘ or a word of appreciation for doing a good job on time motivate the employees and they have a tendency to do jobs on time
- **Give praise in public**: Acknowledge an employee’s achievements in any public forums such as staff meeting etc. will increase the morale of employees
- **Reasonable rewards**: reasonable rewards improves motivation ,in case of certain people ,high rewards will motivate them ,identify those ,and motivate them
- **Financial incentives**: When overtime work is done, provide incentives, .if the work done is more than the targeted appreciate him and provide financial incentives. both the financial and non-financial incentives will motivate the employees
- **Celebrate functions ,enjoyments in business organizations**
- **Conduct tours, workshops, training and development classes etc.**
- **Participate in the employees personal pleasures and with worries**
- **Ask what they want out of work.** Just knowing that an HR manager or boss is interested in a worker's goals will make many employees feel better about their jobs.
- **Consider each employee’s age and life stage.**
- **Pinpoint each employee’s personality.** Some people love public praise; others are mortified by it and would much prefer a sincere, in-person “thank-you.” Make sure you take this into account if you are planning a ceremony to give awards or other recognition.
- **Use flexibility wisely.** Allowing employees to telecommute some of the time or to set their own office hours can have big benefits. It makes employees’ lives more manageable — and it shows them that they are trusted
- **Don’t rely on stock options.** If money is an unreliable motivator, stock options are even less likely to motivate most workers. Employee worth goes up and down with a company’s stock price — something very few workers feel they can control.
- **Offer help with career goals.** When you ask workers what kind of work they enjoy, also find out about what they’re hoping to do in the future. Giving workers opportunities to build the skills and make the connections they need to get ahead in their careers will build loyalty and motivation
- **Help employees learn.** It’s very important for workers to keep learning new skills on the job. With people changing jobs more often than they used to and companies no longer promising long-term employment

Motivation is the key to success in each of our lives. Employees can give their best if they are motivated. Employee’s satisfaction can lead the company to the success. So ever organization and human resource department must ensure their satisfaction and through their satisfaction organizations can motivate employees and it will become a part of organizational change. Achievement, development, and recognition will all come quite naturally to the person, and it is these things which are the true fuels of personal motivation.

5. ORGANISATIONAL CHANGE

An organization is a social entity that has a collective goal and is linked to external environment. There are different types of organizations in our country, government organizations, private, public etc. whatever may be the organizations it consists of men, machinery etc. and their objective may be charity or profit making or providing services etc. All the team members of organizations must be directed towards the common objective of an organization. All the team members must contribute for the development of organizations in order to improve the organizational efficiency and for the proper functioning of every organization, all of its employees must be motivated and developed in a proper manner.

Organizational change refers to the complete change of an organization. There may be two types of changes in an organization. Short term change and long term change. Short term change does not require active participation or any contribution of employees. It will be automatically happen. But there may be labor turn over, absent of efficient employees, lack of continuous productivity etc. It is a normal process that is happened when the employee is joined in the organization and that encouragement will exist only for a short time. But for the long term change and continuous improvement of organizations, effective functioning, survival of business organizations, efficient and active employees are required. Management must be efficient, active, motivated and well worse towards the organization, committed to others responsible with others, and they must have a feeling that the organization is their own. At that time they will be motivated and it will leads to a drastic and strategic change of an organization.

In the present changing and challenging business environment, competition was increasing, every business organizations are adopting strategies to overcome others strategy, business world is now become more complex and tough. In order to overcome it and for the long term survival of business organizations, a strategic change was essential and it will be possible only through managing their stress and effective motivation. So stress management and human resource motivation are vital for the strategic change of organizations

6. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS MANAGEMENT, H.R. MOTIVATION AND ORGANISATIONAL CHANGE

The relationship between stress management, human resource motivation and organizational change can be expressed in the following way

Full of stress

+

+ No motivation

=

= failure and winding up of organization

Full of stress

+

+ full motivation

=

no change

Reduced stress

+

+ full motivation

=

partial change

No stress + full motivation = strategic change

7. FINDINGS SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

- Motivation will completely effective only when there is no stress
- Highly motivated persons never feel stress ,they will be active in organizations
- Identify the causes for organizational stress ,eliminate and motivate them for making them efficient
- Moderate stress in work place is necessary for improving organizational performances.
- Financial rewards, good employee-employer relationship, focusing on strength, etc. can be effectively used as motivational techniques.
- Prioritizing, time scheduling, planning etc., can be effectively used as stress management techniques.
- Reducing of stress , higher motivation will leads to the strategic change of organizations

In nutshell stress and motivation are two sides of a coin. If stress is not eliminated, motivation does not work. There exist a positive relation between stress and motivation. If stress is reduced, high motivational efforts are provided, the employee efficiency will increase, their capacity will increase, they will be active, all the efforts will be effective, organizational efficiency, and productivity etc., will increase strategically. So every organization must try to understand the reasons for stress, reduce it continuously, eliminate it, motivate them frequently manage them effectively for a bright future of human resources and of the organizations.

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